

INTERNET'S POTENTIAL AS A SOURCE OF LEGAL INFORMATION

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Abstract. *The article examines the role and importance of Internet sources in modern legal research. The main focus is on the steady growth of the place and the importance of Internet sources in modern research. The article reveals the features of the Internet as a source of legal information; the problem of authenticity of Internet sources of normative acts in a modern world through critical analysis of the current situation in the world. In conclusion, the article focuses on the importance of studying "information law" as a new scientific branch in legal studies.*

Keywords: *online source, internet, research, information, law and legal, network, document, "information law".*

INTRODUCTION

Today, information plays a fundamental role in the life of all mankind. If there is an exchange of information and experience, it becomes possible to disseminate new technologies and inventions. Therefore, throughout its existence, humanity has sought to exchange information, as it has always been the most important driving force of evolution.

Getting new information is essential for a person to live a full life. Today, there are many ways for individuals to receive information, including traditional channels like newspapers, magazines, and radio broadcasts, and modern channels like Internet news channels, social networks, and blogs.

This process is greatly influenced by the use of Internet resources.

The Internet has turned into a global information system, without which the individual and society are no longer able to carry out effective life activities, receiving the right information at the right time. According to W.F. Ahrens, the Internet is the backbone that is the fastest-growing medium in history.

Global Statshot analysis for July 2023 shows that the number of Internet users has more than doubled over the past 10 years, from 2.18 billion at the beginning of 2012 to 5.19 billion at the beginning of July 2023. This figure corresponds to 64.5 percent of the world's population, although reporting delays means that actual Internet penetration is likely higher than these figures suggest.

The latest GWI survey shows that "search for information" remains the main reason for using the Internet, with more than 6 out of 10 working-age Internet users (61.0%) citing it as the main motivation for using the Internet. And here it can be indicated that the search for information may include, among other things, the search for information for research, and the search for legal information.

Modern technical capabilities allow people to interact not only in real life but also through the use of new publicly available technologies (smartphones, portable and desktop computers, etc.), including through the use of social networks, instant messengers, which today have become one of the main sources of information.

The conducted research shows that the number of global Internet users and their network activity has a steady growth trend. At the same time, the global Internet audience currently accounts for more than half of the world's population. The exchange of information between people is increasingly carried out using social networks, instant messengers, e-mail resources, and various kinds of forums.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The state has always taken care to inform the citizens of the adopted laws and, accordingly, the implementation of these laws. It is believed that the dissemination and accessibility of legal information contribute to the development of the need for broad segments of the population to constantly measure their actions with existing legislation, and this, in turn, leads to the strengthening of the legal foundations of statehood. The provisions or rules of publication are contained in various acts - special acts on publication, and laws on normative legal acts. Most often, the functions of ensuring the publication of regulatory legal acts are assigned to the government.

Given the development of the Internet, the organization of access to legal information has become an important means of disseminating legal information. One of the main factors that influenced the use of Internet technologies for the official publication of regulatory documents was the recognition of the legal force of electronic documents on par with documents recorded on paper. However, the publication of legal acts on the Internet is not always recognized as an official publication. The official form of publication in many countries remains the printed (paper) version of the document. The publication of acts on Internet sites, according to lawyers in many countries, is an additional tool used by the state to disseminate legal information and does not generate legal consequences.

RESULTS

The electronic form of official publication (promulgation) of regulatory legal acts has come to life due to several advantages that Internet technologies represent:

- High speed of information transmission over communication channels;
- Relative (compared to paper) low cost and convenience of storing documents in electronic form;
- Simplicity and ease of access to information resources using web technologies;
- Ease of searching for information in databases;
- The possibility of unlimited copying and replicating, etc.

With the development of information technologies, many States have resorted to publishing electronic versions of official printed publications. At the same time, the fundamental principles are the free use of an electronic publication, its availability at any time of the day, ensuring the rights of those who do not have access to the Internet (public libraries), and guaranteeing the identity of printed and electronic information.

DISCUSSION

At the same time, several States provide Internet access to documents adopted by public authorities, and often this means not just maintaining their websites by the authorities, but also their consolidated version of a special national website. Access to legislative acts is also duplicated on special sites dedicated exclusively to the publication of normative texts.

Typically, both the paper and electronic versions are official. At the same time, according to the Freedom of Information by Electronic Means Act of Hungary, it is the printed (paper) version that is considered true if they differ.

The co-existence of electronic and paper versions of regulatory acts creates the need to address the following issues:

- How to ensure the authenticity of the paper and electronic versions of the document;
- Which version has priority,
- In what order the publication should take place,
- The primacy of publication and the procedure for the act's entry into force.

The study of foreign experience allows us to state that at present the electronic method of publishing regulations on Internet sites complements the traditional – printed one. In case of doubts about their authenticity, in most cases, the priority of the paper version is recognized. An exclusively electronic publication procedure sufficient for the entry into force of the act exists only in a few countries and concerns a limited number of acts of a highly specialized or individual nature.

The Internet itself cannot be a source of legal information. The Internet is only a means for obtaining legal information that is formed by people. For law enforcement practice, official legal information originating from authorized state bodies, which has legal significance and is aimed at regulating public relations, is of particular importance. The problems of access to legal information in the narrow sense in which the task of collecting and presenting legal acts on the Internet was set is currently not relevant, although there are many other organizational and technical tasks.

The Internet is only a way of remote access to information and its visualization using computer technology and communication systems.

A special place should be given to online research. Online research is a research method that involves collecting information on the Internet. With the advent of the Internet, traditional pen-and-paper research methods have faded into the background and made way for online research.

Modern trends in the development of sciences show that the institutionalization of online research is taking place before our eyes and with our participation. Using the Internet to reach consumers is no longer a novelty; significantly increased confidence in the data collected online; there comes a stage when the quality of the work of providers of online research and panels, their compliance with international standards in this field, becomes more significant.

In online research, the Internet is primarily a means and environment for research, a tool for collecting data. The Internet appears in online research in connection with the methodology and technique of empirical research, while the research itself may be devoted to problems not related to the Internet itself.

CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusion of the study is that for the first time, human society is faced with the need to regulate relations in almost all areas of activity in connection with the use of the Internet. Never before have scientific and technological achievements had such a significant impact on the transformation of public life in such a short period by historical standards. The problems of informatization in the field of providing access to legal information are a reflection of the problems in building a modern information society.

The most important conclusion in the study of the presentation of legal information on the Internet is that both the official publication of regulatory acts and the wide presentation of various types of reference systems increase the level of legal culture that contributes to the "development of the individual, group or public legal awareness".

Taking into account the above-mentioned, the most interesting research about the Internet is the study of "information law", as a scientific branch in jurisprudence, which is based on a new paradigm of relations between individuals and legal entities using the global Internet, in the creation and improvement of which millions of people around the world are involved. Currently, most experts believe that information law is a sub-branch of civil or administrative law. The research results show the need to consider this scientific discipline as an independent branch of law due to the comprehensive penetration of Internet technologies into all spheres of human life. At the same time, it will be quite a time-consuming process not only to work on improving regulatory legal acts as sources of law but also to implement the law in all its forms and methods. Constant analysis of the actual circumstances of cases, developing in a multi-vector space, the choice and interpretation of legal norms, qualification works, etc. All these are necessary conditions for the legitimate and justified application of the law. From the point of view of automating the processes of providing legal information, the issues of automating law-making activities throughout the entire "life cycle" of legal documents and creating technical regulations that ensure this activity is considered relevant.

REFERENCES

1. Ibragimov, K. (2022). Some features of modern trends in legal research. *Science and innovation, 1(C5)*, 65-69.
2. Arens, W.F. (2006) *Contemporary advertising*. Boston: McGraw Hill Irwin
3. Digital 2023 July Global Statshot Report. (Date of application: 10.08.23) <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2023-july-global-statshot>
4. Никитин Ю.А. Глобальная сеть интернет как источник информации, значимой для расследования уголовных дел. (Дата обращения – 13.05.2023) <https://etalonline.by/novosti/mnenie/globalnaya-set-internet>
5. Лазарев, В. М., & Барановский, А. Г. (2013). Решение задач официального опубликования нормативно-правовых документов в сети Интернет. *Правовая информатика*, (2), 29-32.
6. Юрий Рыков, & Олег Нагорный (2017). Область интернет-исследований в социальных науках. *Социологическое обозрение*, 16 (3), 366-394.
7. Ibragimov K. D. Creation of decent conditions for the people-a guarantee of sustainable development // *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*. – 2022. – Т. 12. – №. 1. – С. 283-286.
8. *Basic legal research: tools and strategies* / Amy E. Sloan. Seventh edition. | New York City: Wolters Kluwer, [2018] p. 250-272
9. Ибрагимов, К. Д. (2020). Нормативно-правовое регулирование оценки воздействия актов законодательства в сфере развития институтов гражданского общества. *Интернаука*, (23-1), 63-65.